

THE COLONIAL ORIGINS OF HYBRID CONFLICT MANAGEMENT IN CENTRAL NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The dominant hybridity literature locates hybrid conflict management as a response to the failures of liberal peacebuilding in post-Cold War states. This paper argues that this temporal framing misreads the nature of hybrid security arrangements in postcolonial Africa. Drawing on archival sources, oral interviews, and a historical research design covering Nigeria's Middle Belt from the 1920s to 2018, it makes a two-stage argument. First, the structural preconditions for hybrid conflict management were established in the 1920s and 1930s through British colonial governance, specifically the dual administration of emirate and non-emirate communities and the introduction of a Yan Doka force that was ethnically compromised and functionally inadequate for inter-group conflict. Second, these preconditions were institutionalised as a working hybrid architecture during the decolonisation decade of the late 1940s and 1950s, when the Macpherson Constitution, chieftaincy grading, and the strategic collaboration of educated elites with traditional rulers consolidated the tripartite conflict management structure that postcolonial governments inherited. Drawing on two independent empirical genealogies of hybrid governance in the same region, the paper further demonstrates that post-independence shocks deepened rather than created these arrangements and that women developed a fourth conflict management mode operating outside the official tripartite structure, a dimension the hybridity literature has not addressed. The paper connects these genealogies to the international hybridity debate, arguing that the field's temporal blind spot cannot be corrected without systematic engagement with African colonial administrative history.*

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Introduction

Hybrid conflict management, understood as the overlapping and interpenetrating operations of state and non-state actors in managing violent conflict, has become one of the most productive frameworks in contemporary peace and security studies. Since Mac Ginty¹ and Richmond² identified the hybrid turn in peacebuilding, scholars have theorised hybridity as a response to the failures of liberal peace, a product of the encounter between internationally driven statebuilding agendas and the resilience of local, informal, and traditional governance. Bagayoko, Hutchful, and Luckham³ extended this logic to African security sectors, arguing that hybrid security governance captures the complex intersections of formal and informal, state and non-state systems that characterise security provision across the continent. The analytical utility of this framework is real. Its temporal assumptions, however, remain largely unexamined.

The dominant narrative places the emergence of hybrid security in the post-Cold War period,

when the collapse of bipolar geopolitics, the proliferation of intrastate wars, and the rise of liberal peacebuilding interventions created the conditions for hybridity to flourish. Where colonial history appears in this literature, it functions as a backdrop rather than as an object of systematic analytical attention. This paper argues that the hybridity literature has consequently misread the nature of hybrid security arrangements in postcolonial states, treating as innovations what are more accurately understood as continuities. An important parallel genealogy in the external scholarship comes from Jimam Lar,⁴ whose historical study of plural policing in Plateau State traces a direct genealogy from the institutionalisation of paramountcy in the late colonial period through the dismantling of the Native Authority Police Force in 1969, the local government reforms of 1976, and the Structural Adjustment-era vigilantism of the 1980s. Back by empirical data, Lar argues that contemporary plural policing in Plateau State is not a post-Cold War product but a historically layered formation with its roots in the last decade of British colonialism. His work is the most empirically based historical account of this genealogy.

¹ Roger Mac Ginty, 'Hybrid Peace: The Interaction between Top-down and Bottom-up Peace', *Security Dialogue* 41, no. 4 (2010): 391–412.

² Oliver P Richmond, 'A Post-Liberal Peace: Eirenism and the Everyday', *Review of International Studies* 35, no. 3 (2009): 557–80.

³ Niagalé Bagayoko, Eboe Hutchful, and Robin Luckham, 'Hybrid Security Governance in Africa: Rethinking the Foundations of Security, Justice and Legitimate Public Authority',

Conflict, Security and Development 16, no. 1 (2016): 1–32, doi:10.1080/14678802.2016.1136137.

⁴ Jimam T Lar, 'Vigilantism, State, and Society in Plateau State, Nigeria: A History of Plural Policing (1950 to the Present)' (PhD Thesis, University of Bayreuth, 2015), <https://epub.uni-bayreuth.de/id/eprint/2798/>.

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Comparative postcolonial scholarship on policing adds an important dimension. A 2023 study of policing legacies in Pakistan and Nigeria demonstrates that the British co-opted and redefined existing native institutions rather than building a new policing apparatus from scratch, producing a repressive and authoritarian colonial policing model that continued post-independence and contributed to police impunity and the use of force for political ends⁵. The Middle Belt case extends and complicates this comparative finding, as co-optation here was not straightforward but contested, producing a structurally hybrid force whose community legitimacy was compromised from its inception.

This paper builds on the author's prior research and on Lar's parallel genealogy, extending both by pushing the archival argument further back to the 1920s and 1930s and arguing that the structural preconditions for hybrid conflict management were established in that decade through the dual administrative structure and the introduction of the *Yan Doka* force, even if the full institutionalisation of hybrid arrangements came later in the decolonisation decade. Most importantly, this research provides an analytical synthesis that neither of the two studies offers by connecting these separate genealogies to the larger global discourse on hybridity. A limited focus on current structures or recent historical

changes cannot address the intrinsic chronological blind spot of hybridity literature. Instead, this study requires a methodical approach to colonial administrative history, similar to that of Lar and the author's previous studies, and it expands into the area of theoretical reconfiguration.

The scope of this study comprises Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa states located in central Nigeria. It is home to over 200 ethnic minority groups and records one of Nigeria's most severe and recurring conflict casualties. Drawing on archival materials from the Endangered Archives Programme at the British Library and the archives from the department of history & International Studies oral interviews conducted between 2019 and 2021; and the secondary historical scholarship on colonial and post-colonial governance in the region, the paper traces how colonial governance laid structural preconditions in the 1920s and 1930s, how these were institutionalised in the 1940s and 1950s, and how post-independence shocks deepened these arrangements.

Preceding section 1, section 2 examines the hybridity literature, identifies its temporal blind spot, and situates both the author's prior research and Lar's parallel genealogy in relation to the argument. Section 3 identifies the structural preconditions for hybrid conflict management that emerged in the 1920s and 1930s. Section 4

⁵ Zoha Waseem, 'A Postcolonial Condition of Policing?: Exploring Policing and Social Movements in Pakistan and Nigeria', in *Decolonising the Criminal Question*, ed. Ana Aliverti et al., 1st edn (Oxford University Press, Oxford, 20 Dec 2023),

89–106, doi:10.1093/oso/9780192899002.003.0006.

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addresses the decolonisation decade, demonstrating it to be the critical moment of institutionalisation that bridges colonial design and post-independence inheritance. Section 5 traces post-colonial continuities through to 2018. Section 6 draws out the theoretical implications, and Section 7 concludes.

The Hybridity Literature, Its Temporal Blind Spot, and the Case for a Colonial Genealogy

The concept of hybrid conflict management emerged as a sustained intellectual response to the liberal peacebuilding paradigm associated with Roland Paris⁶. He argued post-conflict societies would produce durable peace if they replicated democratic institutions and market economies from the global North. Critics thought differently; they argued that this model failed not only in execution but also in design because it did not consider the existing governance arrangements in the societies it sought to transform.

For example, Mac Ginty⁷ contends that a state that practises hybrid peace is neither entirely imposed by external sources nor completely local but arises from the interplay of liberal and non-liberal norms, actors, and practices. Richmond⁸ theorised hybridity as the unintended consequence of liberal statebuilding encountering the

everyday resistance of local communities. Both accounts anchor themselves in the post-Cold War conjuncture. Boege, Brown, and Clements⁹ extended this framework to the question of statehood, arguing that what appears to be 'state failure' in the global South is better understood as the coexistence of hybrid political orders. Bagayoko, Hutchful, and Luckham¹⁰ account of hybrid security governance from the African context, argue that across African security sectors, formal and informal systems, and state and non-state actors, do not operate in separate lanes but overlap and work through one another in ways that resist simple categorisation. Crucially, their framework treats this as a normal feature of African governance rather than as a symptom of state failure

What these contributions share is a tendency towards presentist methodological approach where colonial history often manifests in one of two unsatisfactory ways. The first is the acknowledgement that colonialism created the ethnic divisions and governance legacies that shape contemporary politics, without tracing the institutional pathways through which those legacies produced contemporary hybrid arrangements. The second is as an explanation of state weak-

⁶ Roland Paris, *At War's End: Building Peace after Civil Conflict* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004).

⁷ Mac Ginty, 'Hybrid Peace: The Interaction between Top-down and Bottom-up Peace'.

⁸ Richmond, 'A Post-Liberal Peace: Eirenism and the Everyday'.

⁹ Volker Boege, M Anne Brown, and Kevin P Clements, 'Hybrid Political Orders, Not Fragile States', *Peace Review* 21, no. 1 (2009): 13–21.

¹⁰ Bagayoko, Hutchful, and Luckham, 'Hybrid Security Governance in Africa: Rethinking the Foundations of Security, Justice and Legitimate Public Authority'.

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ness, invoking colonial extraction and administrative disruption to illustrate why postcolonial states lack the capacity to monopolise the legitimate use of force, thereby creating the vacuum that hybrid security actors fill. Neither of the two approaches analyses colonial administration as the structural origin of hybridity itself.

However, the architects of the hybridity framework have recently begun to acknowledge these limitations. Mac Ginty¹¹ revisits and updates the concept of hybridity based on the fragmented, multipolar international system, arguing that earlier accounts of hybrid peace and hybrid political orders tended to be Eurocentric and were usually used as a way of understanding relationships between Western liberal peace actors on the one hand and national and local actors on the other. His call to broaden the range of actors and to consider external factors that shape peace and conflict environments serves as an important corrective.

This paper builds on Mac Ginty's correction. Earlier accounts of hybridity had two blind spots. They focused mainly on Western actors, and they assumed that hybrid governance was a recent, post-Cold War development. Mac Ginty addresses the first blind spot by bringing in a wider range of actors. But he does not address the second. Broadening who counts as an actor, without

also asking when hybridity actually began, leaves the field's deeper assumption untouched. The Central Nigeria case shows what it means to tackle both blind spots at once.

Frederick Cooper's¹² methodological critique of Mahmood Mamdani¹³ is particularly applicable here. Cooper accuses Mamdani's decentralised despotism framework of leapfrogging. This practice involves claiming that an event in time A caused an event in time C, while neglecting to consider what transpired in time B. Cooper argues that Mamdani links colonial administration in the 1920s and 1930s to failed democratisation in the 1980s and 1990s, while almost entirely overlooking the decolonisation decade, thereby missing the critical processes of mobilisation, negotiation, and transformation that occurred during that period.

This critique has a direct impact on any theory that asserts a colonial origin for contemporary hybrid security arrangements. If the reasoning proceeds directly from colonial structure to post-independence outcome without considering the intervening decades, the resulting causal explanation is structurally deterministic and historically shallow. This paper takes the risk seriously. Section 4 devotes significant analytical attention

¹¹ Roger Mac Ginty, 'The Liberal Peace Is over and It Is Not Coming Back: Hybridity and the Emerging International Peace System', *Third World Quarterly* 46, no. 16 (2 November 2025): 1999–2018, doi:10.1080/01436597.2025.2559376.

¹² Frederick Cooper, *Colonialism in Question: Theory,*

Knowledge, History (Univ of California Press, 2005).

¹³ Mahmood Mamdani, *Citizen and Subject, Contemporary Africa and the Legacy of Late Colonialism* (New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 1996).

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to the decade of decolonisation. The closest existing study in the empirical literature is Lar¹⁴, whose thesis on plural policing in Plateau State demonstrates that contemporary policing plurality in Central Nigeria can be traced to the institutionalisation of paramountcy in the chieftaincy institutions of the Plateau Province from the early 1940s to the late 1950s. Lar considers three successive institutional developments as constitutive; these include the dismantling of the Native Authority Police Force in 1969, local government reforms in 1976, and state-directed vigilantism during the SAP era in the 1980s. He sees traditional rulership as the fundamental institutional link between these periods, arguing that traditional rulers creatively responded to the loss of their statutory enforcement arm by forming and authorising *Yanbanga* vigilante organisations. His research, which includes interviews with former NAPF officers, Civil War veterans who started *Yanbanga*, and current VGN members, produces a historically textured account that no purely contemporary analysis of plural policing in the region could replicate.

In an earlier study, the author documented state and non-state dynamics across Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa from 1957 to 2018, establishing that hybrid conflict management predated liberal peacebuilding and traced its origins to the colonial period when the emirate system oper-

ated alongside non-emirate administrative structures. That study treated the colonial period as contextual grounding, drawing on secondary scholarship rather than original archival research, and did not connect its findings to the international hybridity literature. This paper extends that prior work in two directions. First, it deepens the colonial genealogy through original archival evidence from the Endangered Archives Programme and the National Archives Kaduna, including the *Yan Doka*'s ethnic composition, the 1931 *Ruga* placement procedure, and the 1934 court jurisdiction failures, establishing the structural preconditions of the 1920s and 1930s as an independent archival argument. Second, it makes the theoretical connection to the international hybridity debate that the earlier study left unmade.

This paper has two goals that neither the earlier study nor Lar's work achieved. First, it pushes the genealogy back to the 1920s and 1930s. The earlier study could not reach that far because its research began in 1957. Second, it draws out what both the earlier study and Lar's research mean for the international hybridity debate, a connection that neither makes explicitly. This paper also differs from Lar in what it examines. Lar is concerned with policing, by which he means crime control and the maintenance of law and order. This paper is concerned with conflict

¹⁴ Lar, 'Vigilantism, State, and Society in Plateau State, Nigeria: A History of Plural Policing (1950 to the Present) '.

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management, meaning the governance of violence between ethnic, religious, and economic communities. The two overlap, but they are not the same thing, and the difference matters. The hybrid arrangements in Central Nigeria were shaped by the challenge of managing violence between communities in a region of extraordinary ethnic complexity. That challenge is distinct from controlling crime, and it explains why the hybrid architecture took the specific form it did. Lar's policing-focused genealogy does not include the farmer-herder mediation machinery, the tribal union advocacy function, or the management of indigene-settler tensions, which are at the heart of this paper's empirical thesis. Theoretically, Lar does not engage with the international hybridity literature. The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate that the genealogy Lar establishes has direct and unacknowledged repercussions for international scholarship, which has been theorising what African administrative history shows to be inherited as novel.

Structural Preconditions for Hybrid Conflict Management, 1920s to Early 1940s

When the British established Plateau Province in 1926 through the reorganisation of the Muri, Nasarawa and Bauchi provinces, they formalised a dual administrative architecture that had been

taking shape since the early years of colonial rule. Lugard's Indirect Rule model used the Fulani-led emirate system as the template for Native Authority governance, but the Middle Belt did not fit that template. Colonial archival records, analysed in detail by Mangvwat,¹⁵ explained how the attempt by British colonial administrators to create paramount chiefs in non-emirate communities went through four successive phases between 1900 and the 1930s, each of which ended in failure. Lar draws on some of the same archival sources in his study of plural policing and reaches compatible conclusions, and the convergence of two independent historical studies strengthens the evidential basis for the argument made here. Ethnic groups like the Berom, Ngas, Goemai, Mwaghavul, Eggon, and Tarok comprised several independent polities each with their priest chiefs, clan heads, and customary dispute resolution mechanisms. Appointing a paramount chief over communities that had no history of such authority created precisely the conditions for conflict that the appointment was meant to prevent.¹⁶

The colonial administration also created four Hausa village areas, and headmen administered them with explicit authority over non-indigenous settler populations¹⁷. This spatial arrangement

¹⁵ Monday Yakiban Mangvwat, *History of Class Formation in the Plateau Province of Nigeria, 1902-1960: The Genesis of the Ruling Class* (Durham: Carolina Academic Press, 2013).

¹⁶ Shendam Division Plateau Province [June 6, 1936]" (British Library, n.d.), <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-9-10>; Ames, *Gazetteers of the Northern Province of Nigeria*

¹⁷ While Ames does not mention the four Hausa Village areas, the Jasawa association, which has claimed ownership of Jos since 1994, argues that Abba Nashehu, Garba Daho, Ibrahim Katsina, Sarki Arab, Gangare, and Ali Kazaure constitute the Jos Native Town. For additional information on the complexities of Jos ownership, see Plotnicov, L. (1972). *Who Owns Jos?*

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produced a jurisdictional dualism that was the structural foundation of conflict management in the region. Under this system, indigenous districts were governed by co-opted traditional authorities, settler zones were governed by Hausa headmen with colonial backing, and there was a grey zone of competing claims between them that neither system could unambiguously adjudicate. The principle of indigenous ownership, which gave recognised autochthonous communities indigenes preferential access to schools, civil service appointments, and political representation, was a colonial creation that made the distinction between indigene and settler the most consequential social fact in Middle Belt political life, entrenching the very conflict dynamic it was nominally designed to manage.

The colonial production of this distinction and its postcolonial consequences have been traced empirically in the same regional context by Longbaam-Alli¹⁸, who demonstrates that the 1900 Land Acquisition Ordinance altered customary tenure and formed the roots of post-colonial land grabbing, with the 1978 Land Use Act further dismantling traditional conflict resolution by concentrating land authority and generating zero-sum competition between communities. Their

analysis of Central Nigeria confirms that hybrid approaches to conflict management emerge precisely from these institutional gaps but cannot address them without comprehensive reform of the colonial land policy inheritance.

These institutional arrangements are the structural preconditions for hybrid conflict management, not its realisation. The colonial administration's inability to construct a workable central authority in the non-emirate communities meant that inter-group conflict could never be delegated entirely to a single paramount institution. Governing inter-group violence in the Middle Belt required coordination between state authority, traditional authority, and the communities themselves from the outset. This coordination was not hybrid governance in any designed sense. It was the institutionalisation of ambiguity, and ambiguity is the structural precondition of hybridity.

The Native Authority Police Force (NAPF), reorganised as the *Yan Doka* of the Jos Division in May 1937, was the coercive instrument through which colonial conflict management was supposed to operate at the local level. Both the archival research underpinning this study and Lar's¹⁹ thesis on plural policing document that in

Ethnic Ideology in Nigerian Urban Politics In Urban Anthropology, Spring (Vol. 1, Issue 1). <http://www.jstor.com/stable/40552853>, Plateau Indigenous Development Association Network [PIDAN]. (2010). The History, Ownership, Establishment of and Misconceptions about the recurrent Conflicts. DAN-SiL Press., and Plateau Indigenous Development Association Network, [PIDAN]. (2013). Effects of the Jos/Plateau Conflicts and Crises & their implications on Nigeria's National

Security Vol.2 No.1. LA'ASUK Productions

¹⁸ Gloria Longbaam-Alli, 'Obstructed Paths To Justice: Land Grabbing And The Crisis Of Reconciliation In Central Nigeria's Postcolonial Conflicts', *Revista Brasileira de Estudos Africanos* 10, no. 19 (2025).

¹⁹ Lar, 'Vigilantism, State, and Society in Plateau State, Nigeria: A History of Plural Policing (1950 to the Present)'.

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its early decades, the NAPF in Plateau Province was staffed predominantly by recruits from the northern Hausa emirates rather than from local communities. He provides a specific illustration of this, showing how in 1939, provincial police report recorded that of 206 NAPF men in the province, 68 were Hausa, followed by 34 of Igbo descent, 18 Fulani, and 15 Kanuri. The ethnic character of the force was directly connected to colonial language policy where proficiency in Hausa was a condition for employment because Hausa was the language of instruction at the Police Training Depot in Kaduna and the language of Native Administration across the northern territories.

For non-Muslim Middle Belt communities, the NAPF was not a neutral enforcement body. It was an extension of Hausa-Fulani administrative dominance, staffed by officers perceived as foreign and associated with the sub-colonialism that indirect rule had imposed on the region.²⁰ Lar's thesis identifies two assessments that document the coercive apparatus's limits, including a 1937 memo from the Chief Commissioner of Police acknowledging that in certain rural areas the *Yan Doka* would function as little more than village guards and a 1944 Divisional Officer's assessment of the Shendam force as being filled with illiterate and semi-literate personnel who

were little more than messengers. The archival evidence from this study indicates an additional institutional consequence. An excerpt from the 1934 Plateau Province Annual Report documents that communities refused to use courts presided over by chiefs of other ethnic groups.

The people of Hos would not use the Ganawuri court because it was presided over by a chief of another tribe; the people of Gabong would not go to the Naraguta court because their chief, belonging to the Birom tribe, held no authority over them.²¹

The formal mechanisms of conflict management were accessible only within ethnic communities, not between them, which is precisely where the most consequential conflicts occurred. This coercive deficit is the immediate cause of the non-coercive hybrid mechanisms that colonial administrators improvised to compensate. District officers arbitrated boundary disputes on periodic tours. Administrative sessions at divisional headquarters managed farmer-herder compensation claims. The 1931 procedure for managing *Ruga* placement disputes, which routed herder movement applications through the district head and the Fulani *Ardo* simultaneously, created a structured mediation space grounded in traditional community authority.²² These mechanisms were not designed as a hybrid governance

²⁰ Moses E. Ochonu, *Colonialism by Proxy: Hausa Imperial Agents and Middle Belt Consciousness in Nigeria* (Indiana University Press, 2014).

²¹ Annual Report Plateau Province Department Reports [1934]"

(British Library, EAP532/1/3/12, n.d.), <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-3-12>.

²² Divisional Notes Jos Division," Endangered Archives Programme, April 26, 1913, <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP532-1-11-9>.

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system. They were the improvised operational responses of a colonial administration that could not govern inter-group conflict through force alone.

It is worth noting that the colonial tripartite structure taking shape in this period was an entirely male domain. The chieftaincy system, the *Yan Doka*, and the educated elite networks all operated through male authority, and women had no formal place in any of them. The governance arrangements traced in this section were built without women. How those exclusions were carried forward through the decolonisation decade and into the postcolonial period is beyond the scope of this paper, but the question deserves serious scholarly attention.

The Decolonisation Decade, Institutionalisation and the Bridge to Independence, Late 1940s to 1960

Cooper's²³ leapfrogging critique demands that any argument claiming a colonial genealogy for contemporary hybrid arrangements must account for what happened in the decades between the colonial period and the present. This section addresses that demand directly. The decolonisation decade of the late 1940s to 1960 was not merely a transitional phase between colonial precondition and post-independence inheritance. It was the period in which the structural preconditions for hybrid conflict management were actively institutionalised as a working architecture,

through three overlapping processes, namely constitutional change and chieftaincy grading, the post-war transformation of the NAPF through ex-servicemen, and the strategic collaboration between educated elites and traditional rulers.

The Macpherson Constitution of 1951 created a bicameral legislative system in the Northern Region with a House of Chiefs restricted to graded traditional rulers. The grading requirements, which classified chieftaincies as first, second, third, or fourth class depending on size and history, had an unintended but consequential effect in Plateau Province. Communities without a paramount graded chief were excluded from constitutional representation. This provision created a powerful material incentive for communities to seek paramouncy that four decades of colonial administrative pressure had failed to generate. One ethnic group after another organised ethnic solidarity as the basis for creating paramount chiefs that would meet the grading requirements. Within a decade, paramount chiefs had been installed in communities that had previously resisted such institutions. What the British had tried to impose by administrative fiat and failed for four decades was achieved through the constitutional incentive structure of the approaching independence²⁴.

The process was not passive. In the case of the Tarok, the educated elites of the Yergam Union

²³ Cooper, *Colonialism in Question: Theory, Knowledge, History*.

²⁴ Lar, 'Vigilantism, State, and Society in Plateau State, Nigeria: A History of Plural Policing (1950 to the Present)'.

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actively persuaded traditional rulers to accept the new chieftaincy arrangements, playing a central role in building the very institutions they would later challenge when their political interests shifted²⁵. This working relationship between educated elites and traditional rulers, aimed at securing constitutional representation, was already a form of hybrid governance in practice, even if no one called it that at the time. State authority, traditional authority, and educated elite advocacy were all operating together toward a shared political goal. The Macpherson period is precisely the time B that Cooper warns against omitting. And our study has noted that scholars most often skip over when drawing a line between colonial structures and post-independence outcomes. Paying close attention to it matters. The chieftaincy institutions that Nigeria inherited at independence in 1960 were not the fragile, disputed structures of the 1920s and 1930s. By 1960, they had been formally recognised, ranked in official grades, and given constitutional standing—all through the determined effort of communities and their educated leaders during the final years of colonial rule.

A parallel shift happened through the return of World War II veterans from 1946 onwards. Before the war, the NAPF had been mainly composed of Hausa recruits drawn from the

northern emirates. After the war, it was transformed by returning soldiers from non-Muslim communities in Plateau Province who had served in Burma as part of the Nigerian Regiment. A 1926 Plateau Province report had already established the policy of preferring recruits with prior military service²⁶. By 1946, the Shendam Division annual report was praising the improvements in the force that came when 'less suitable types' were replaced by 'ex-soldiers of good quality'²⁷.

The importance of this transformation goes beyond questions of police effectiveness. The veterans brought more than military discipline and practical skills. They also carried the authority of men who had gone to war in defence of their communities and come home with new knowledge and broader experience. The NAPF in the late 1940s recruited mainly from veterans not only because educated men had little interest in becoming Yan Doka, but also because veterans commanded a respect that ordinary civilian recruits simply did not. The result was a police force that drew its authority from two sources at once: official appointment by the state and earned standing within the community. That combination was not planned. It was the unintended outcome of post-war demobilisation.

The third process was the growing influence of educated elite organisations. Pressure groups

²⁵ Lar, 'Vigilantism, State, and Society in Plateau State, Nigeria: A History of Plural Policing (1950 to the Present)'.

²⁶ NAK.JosProf 2/18/497/1926, Plateau Province Annual Report for 1926

²⁷ NAK, JosProf 1/1/6451/1947, Plateau Province Annual Report for 1946

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such as the Berom Progressive Union, the Yergam Union, the Tiv Progressive Union, and the Berom Educational and Cultural Organisation gave communities a way to channel their grievances and political ambitions through formal institutions rather than through confrontation. These union groups explicitly committed their organisations towards strengthen solidarity and intervene in all matters affecting their people, including offering guidance to traditional rulers on community interests. This was a form of conflict management. By turning the potential for inter-community violence into constitutional negotiation and political argument, these organisations helped keep disputes from becoming violent. The relationship between these ethnic union groups and their traditional rulers in the 1950s and early 1960s reveals what educated elites could contribute and where they fell short. In the case of the Yergam, Lar explained that the Union initially worked alongside traditional rulers to secure constitutional representation. But when the Ponzhi Tarok, the paramount chief of the Tarok people, sided with the ruling Northern People's Congress against the Union's advice, the relationship broke down. The same pattern played out across the province. The educated elites were commoners without the financial resources that their counterparts in the northern emirates could draw on, and their internal disagreements, between those who wanted a separate

Middle Belt state and those who preferred to work within the existing Northern structure, prevented them from acting as a unified force. They were a necessary part of the architecture, but too divided and too poorly resourced to play that part consistently²⁸.

By 1960, the conditions laid in the 1920s and 1930s had produced a working, if imperfect, governance architecture. At the top sat state authority, in the form of the colonial and then regional government. At the community level sat traditional authority, in the form of paramount chiefs who now held formal constitutional recognition and consolidated standing within their communities. And in the space between them sat the educated elite layer. This architecture was not the product of a single decision or a deliberate plan. It was built up piece by piece through colonial improvisation, constitutional incentives, the return of war veterans who reshaped the social landscape, and the political organising that gathered momentum as independence approached. It came into being without anyone designing it.

Post-Colonial Continuities And Deepened Hybridity, 1960–2018

The post-independence continuities traced in this section engage directly with the author's prior empirical research across Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa from 1957 to 2018, whose findings converge with and extend the genealogy established in Sections 3 and 4²⁹.

²⁸ Lar, 'Vigilantism, State, and Society in Plateau State, Nigeria, p. 112

²⁹ Longba'am, 'Historicising Hybrid Conflict Management: State and Non-State Dynamics in Nigeria's Middle Belt 1957-

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When Nigeria became independent in 1960, it inherited the hybrid conflict management architecture without the will or the capacity to replace it. The Tiv riots of 1960 and 1964 put that inheritance to its first major test. The Nigerian Police Force was simply too small for the scale of the crisis. The Tiv Division had seven police units and 360 officers, facing an estimated 50,000 rioters. The military was deployed. Tellingly, officials of the United Middle Belt Congress, the main political organisation representing Middle Belt minorities, welcomed the military as more neutral than the police³⁰. Communities were already judging conflict management actors not by whether they were state or non-state, but by whether they could be trusted to be fair. The hybrid arrangement was reproducing itself under new political conditions³¹. The hybrid arrangement was reproducing itself under new political conditions.

The same colonial legacy of ethnic division has been documented in the neighbouring Kaduna region by Maiangwa,³² whose ethnographic study shows that British colonisation created the conditions for ongoing disputes over identity and territorial belonging. These colonial divisions hardened ethnic stereotypes and fuelled ethno-

religious intolerance that persists to the present day. Maiangwa's analysis of recurring inter-communal conflicts in Kaduna, also demonstrates the limits of labels like 'farmer-herder conflict' in capturing how deep and structurally rooted these patterns of violence actually are. This paper's historically grounded account speaks directly to that limitation³³.

The military coup of 1966 and the dismantling of the Native Authority Police Force in 1969, which incorporated approximately 9,000 former NAPF officers into the NPF, accelerated the fragmentation of late-colonial structures without replacing them. Lar³⁴ documents how the Ponzhi Tarok called his council's attention to rising crime in 1971, two years after the NAPF was disbanded, directly linking the insecurity to the failure to replace the NAPF with an adequate alternative. What followed was not a spontaneous community reaction. It was a deliberate institutional response: traditional rulers created community vigilante groups, known as Yanbanga, to fill the security gap and preserve their authority. These groups would later become the direct forerunner of the Vigilante Group of Nigeria. The local government reforms of 1976 deepened the problem. By reorganising administrative units and cutting

2018'.

³⁰ Miners, N. J. *The Nigerian Army, 1956–1966*. Studies in African History, vol. 5. (London: Methuen, 1971.)

³¹ Tiv Commission Report ACC/REP/28' (Makurdi: Office of the Premier, Northern Nigeria, 1964).

³² Benjamin Maiangwa, *The Crisis of Belonging and Ethnographies of Peacebuilding in Kaduna State, Nigeria* (Bloomsbury

Publishing PLC, 2021).

³³ Dare Leke Idowu, 'The Crisis of Belonging and Ethnographies of Peacebuilding in Kaduna State, Nigeria, Benjamin Maiangwa', *Africa Today* 68, no. 3 (February 2022): 144–45, doi:10.2979/africatoday.68.3.08.

³⁴ Lar, 'Vigilantism, State, and Society in Plateau State, Nigeria: A History of Plural Policing (1950 to the Present)'.

Gloria Longbaam-Alli (PhD)

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back the formal powers of traditional rulers, the reforms removed the official channels through which traditional leaders had governed their communities, leaving them with little choice but to rely on the vigilante structures that the colonial period had first improvised³⁵.

Two post-independence shocks deepened the institutional hybridity that the colonial and late-colonial periods had established. The Nigerian Civil War of 1967 to 1970 introduced a new generation of demobilised soldiers into the hybrid policing landscape. Civil war veterans, unable to be absorbed by the NPF, became the core training component of the Yanbanga groups of the 1970s. For example, the first generation of Yanbanga in Langtang North and Shendam were drawn predominantly from civil war veterans, replicating at a postcolonial level the same socialisation dynamic that had transformed the late-colonial NAPF³⁶.

The Structural Adjustment Programme of 1986 accelerated the de-statisation of service delivery. Lar and Longbaam attest that the process was a critical turning point in the deepening of hybrid security arrangements across the Middle Belt.

Lar's account of the SAP-era Yanbanga establishment documents that the vigilante groups of the 1980s were not spontaneous community responses to state withdrawal but explicitly state-directed formations. Maiangwa Chenvong Vongbut's account, as recorded by Lar, describes traditional rulers being summoned to Abuja, given directives about the policing shortfall, and told to select community members for vigilante appointment. Letters of appointment were issued and monthly allowances paid. The Nigerian government mobilised the population through Police Community Relations Committees as a form of community policing. This was state-authorised co-optation from above, formalising the traditional ruler and vigilante infrastructure that decades of hybrid practice had already established³⁷. Longba'am's research across Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa documents the complementary dimension: communities actively adapted to the same security vacuum through local initiative, demonstrating that the hybrid character of the 1980s Yanbanga formations operated simultaneously from above and below³⁸. The contemporary hybrid conflict management arrangements in Plateau, Benue and Nasarawa

³⁵ Longbaam-Alli, 'Obstructed Paths To Justice: Land Grabbing And The Crisis Of Reconciliation In Central Nigeria's Postcolonial Conflicts'.

³⁶ Lar, "Vigilantism, State, and Society," chap. 5; Longba'am, "Historicising Hybrid Conflict Management," chap. 5. The convergence of two independent oral history projects on this finding from Lar's interviews in Plateau State and Longba'am's across Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa strengthens the evidential basis for the claim.

³⁷ Lar, 'Vigilantism, State, and Society in Plateau State, Nigeria: A History of Plural Policing (1950 to the Present)'.

³⁸ Longba'am, 'Historicising Hybrid Conflict Management', chap. 5, pp. 179–186. Where Lar emphasises state direction from above as the organising logic of SAP-era Yanbanga formation, Longba'am's oral history research across Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa foregrounds community initiative from below as an equally constitutive dimension of the same process. The two accounts are complementary rather than contradictory

Gloria Longbaam-Alli (PhD)

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states display the tripartite architecture traced across this paper, now formalised and bureaucratically elaborated. In Plateau State, hybrid security initiatives institutionalised the cooperation between state security agencies and non-state actors including vigilante groups, hunter associations, and community watch organisations. In Benue State, the Agro Rangers combined state authorisation with community recruitment. In Nasarawa, community policing programmes incorporated traditional rulers as legitimating authorities for vigilante deployment. In all three states, the basic institutional logic was the same, with state authority at the apex, traditional authority at the community level, and organised civil actors in the intermediary space. This is not a recent innovation produced by the failure of liberal peacebuilding. It is the colonial architecture operating within democratic and security-sector frameworks rather than colonial ones.

The institutional origins of Operation Rainbow illustrate this colonial logic reproducing itself under democratic conditions with particular clarity. As Longbaam demonstrates, Operation Rainbow was not created as a response to the failure of liberal peacebuilding frameworks. It emerged from a specific constitutional bottleneck, since the federal-state authority hierarchy meant that a state governor could not deploy military resources without presidential clearance, and the pace of escalating violence made that

clearance process structurally inadequate. Governor Jonah David Jang's solution of a hybrid security structure established on 23 June 2010 combining state-authorized vigilante groups with the Plateau State joint task force was not a new design. It was the colonial logic of coordinating state, traditional, and civil actors at the community level, recast in democratic idiom to circumvent a constitutional obstacle. By 2016, Benue State had replicated this model through the Agro Rangers, and Nasarawa had institutionalised community policing through Governor Tanko Al Makura's standing committee, which ensured representation of all aggrieved groups at local government, ward, and unit levels³⁹.

The tripartite architecture as formalised across these three states reproduced a structural exclusion that runs through the entire genealogy traced in this paper. Longba'am's research across Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa establishes that gender was not mainstreamed into the activities of vigilante organisations in any of the three states. Across the VGN, female members were recruited in part because they could conduct investigations in purdah contexts where male officers could not operate but these were functional accommodations rather than structural integration. In exceptional cases, women participated in patrols and stop-and-search activities in Barkin Ladi and Jos. Male vigilante members consistently restricted women from night patrols and confined their roles to advisory and intelligence

³⁹ Longba'am, 'Historicising Hybrid Conflict Management',

pp. 179–186.

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functions. This was not an operational oversight. It was the colonial pattern reproduced: the coercive and governmental layers of the architecture remained male, and women's contributions were accommodated at the margins of an institutional structure that had never been designed to include them⁴⁰.

What Longba'am's research additionally reveals is that women in the Middle Belt developed a fourth mode of conflict management that operated outside and alongside the official tripartite structure. Beginning in August 2002, women took to protests demanding the prosecution of perpetrators of the incessant killings and judicial reform of the indigene-settler status that colonial governance had created, women-led conflict management took an organised political form that the tripartite architecture could neither accommodate nor suppress.

From 2002 to 2026, over forty women led protests have become organised interventions combining ethnic solidarity networks, market coalitions, and in some instances the symbolic politics of naked protest, mobilised as a cultural form of shame against state inaction. Cross-religious solidarity consolidated this fourth mode: a Christian-Muslim coalition formed the Plateau Women Peace Initiative (PWPI)⁴¹ as a conflict

management organisation explicitly oriented toward peaceful coexistence across the religious divide. Women were also integrated as the primary intelligence-collection agents in Operation Rainbow's community architecture, operating through the information-gathering protocol at community level. These were not marginal contributions to the hybrid arrangements. They were a structurally necessary supplement to a tripartite system that had been constituted without women and could not function effectively at the community intelligence level without them⁴².

Community-level assessments of the hybrid arrangements in all three states add a further dimension that the administrative record alone cannot capture. Longba'am's oral interview documents widespread popular preference for non-state actors over state security agencies, on grounds of proximity, cultural familiarity, and perceived impartiality, as most respondents considered non-state groups closer to community needs and more credible than state agencies. This popular assessment is itself a product of the colonial governance history traced in this paper. Communities in the Middle Belt assign legitimacy to conflict management actors through the lens of ethnic belonging, communal authority, and informal accountability that British colonial

⁴⁰ Longba'am, 'Historicising Hybrid Conflict Management', pp. 169–170.

⁴¹ Bulus, Kwopnan Ibrahim, Feyza Bhatti, and Cemaliye Beysoylu. "Women's Agency in Peacebuilding in Polarized Post-Conflict Communities in Plateau State, Nigeria." *J. Pol. & L.* 13 (2020): 189.; Ari, Anisah. *Emerging leadership practices*

in extremity: Case study of women advancing collective enterprise in peace building processes, Plateau State, Nigeria. Kansas State University, 2024.

⁴² Longba'am, 'Historicising Hybrid Conflict Management', Section 7.6, pp. 262–267; p. 282.

Gloria Longbaam-Alli (PhD)

governance institutionalised as the ground-level logic of governance in the region. The hybrid architecture is not merely a formal institutional inheritance. It is a lived set of legitimacy expectations that ordinary people bring to conflict management, and those expectations are themselves a product of the colonial period from which this paper's argument begins⁴³.

Recent scholarship confirms the explanatory weight of this colonial genealogy for understanding the persistence of inter-group conflict in the region. Sakupapa et al.⁴⁴ demonstrate that colonial legacies and historical trajectories explain contemporary religious and ethnic tensions in Northern Nigeria, and that constitutional ambiguities inherited from the colonial period continue to compound those legacies. Their finding that colonial history provides the essential analytical key to current hybrid conflict management and peacebuilding in Northern Nigeria independently corroborates the argument this paper develops through archival and historical methods.

Consequences of Colonial *Longue Duree* For Hybridity Theory

The argument advanced in this paper has four implications for the hybridity literature, all of

which flow from taking the colonial genealogy seriously and extending the genealogy Lar establishes into theoretical terrain he does not enter. The first implication concerns temporal framing. The claim that hybridity emerges from the failure of liberal peacebuilding cannot adequately account for the Middle Belt case. Hybrid conflict management arrangements in Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa predate liberal peacebuilding by several decades and were institutionally produced by forces specific to the colonial and late-colonial context rather than by events after the post-Cold War era. Connecting Lar's historical account of policing in Plateau State to the international hybridity debate reveals that what scholars have been treating as a new or recent development was already present and deeply embedded. The hybrid arrangements in the Middle Belt are not a reaction to the failures of liberal peace. They are the latest form of a governance logic whose foundations were laid in the 1920s and whose decisive consolidation happened in the decade before independence.

The Middle Belt case is not exceptional in this regard. Recent scholarship on Somaliland demonstrates that British colonial governance there produced a hybrid model that blended centralised control with selective local participation

⁴³ Longba'am, 'Historicising Hybrid Conflict Management', pp. 267–268. The reference to popular legitimacy criteria also draws on Longba'am's broader oral history sample of 75 interviews conducted in Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa states (2019–2021), including 29 women interviewees, described in her Chapter 1, pp. 35–44.

⁴⁴ Teddy C. Sakupapa and Oladele P. Adehanloye, 'Sacred Contradictions: Religion, Conflict and Peacebuilding in Northern Nigeria', *HTS Theologiese Studies / Theological Studies* 81, no. 1 (14 November 2025): a10969, doi:10.4102/HTS.v81i1.10969.

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through Advisory, Executive, and Local Government Councils between 1946 and 1960, laying a foundation for Somaliland's post-1991 grassroots peacebuilding that continues to distinguish it from southern Somalia's trajectory⁴⁵. The comparison is instructive. In both Central Nigeria and Somaliland, the hybrid governance arrangements that today's scholars attribute to post-Cold War innovations in peacebuilding were in fact rooted in experiments that took shape in the final years of colonial rule, and their effects continued long after colonial rule ended. The Middle Belt is therefore not a special case. It is one example of a broader pattern across Africa in which colonial history produced hybrid governance arrangements that the hybridity literature has yet to examine in any systematic way.

The second implication concerns the leapfrogging problem. This paper has addressed Cooper's methodological challenge by identifying the decolonisation decade as the decisive moment of institutionalisation that connects structural preconditions to post-independence inheritance. The Macpherson Constitution, chieftaincy grading, the post-war transformation of the NAPF through ex-servicemen, and the strategic collaboration between educated elites and traditional rulers in pursuit of constitutional representation were the processes through which structural am-

biguity became a working architecture. Any account of the colonial genealogy of hybrid security in the Middle Belt that omits this decade cannot explain the specific institutional form that hybrid arrangements took in the postcolonial period.

The third implication, and the most significant departure from Lar, is about methodology. Lar's thesis is a historical account of policing institutions written for Nigerian policing scholars and aimed at debates about policing reform. It does not engage with the hybridity literature and does not claim to. This paper does. The implication goes beyond simply adding historical depth to an existing body of scholarship. If hybrid conflict management in postcolonial Africa is a product of colonial history rather than a recent response to the failures of post-Cold War peacebuilding, then the frameworks built by previous scholars of hybridity need to be fundamentally rethought for the African context. As they currently stand, those frameworks can describe what hybrid governance looks like and how it operates. What they cannot do is explain where it came from or why it takes the particular institutional shapes it does in any particular country. This finding converges, from a historical rather than an ethnographic angle, with Millar's⁴⁶ argument that hybrid institutions were never designed to produce predictable local experiences, and the Middle Belt case shows that the colonial origins of hybrid

⁴⁵ Yasmin Hashem, 'One Nation, Two Paths: Colonial Legacies and the Divergent Statehoods of Somalia and Somaliland', pdf (University of Chicago, 2025), doi:10.6082/UCHI-CAGO.15251.

⁴⁶ Gearoid Millar, 'Disaggregating Hybridity Why Hybrid Institutions Do Not Produce Predictable Experiences of Peace', *Journal of Peace Research*, 2014, doi:10.1177/0022343313519465.

Gloria Longbaam-Alli (PhD)

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conflict management were themselves improvised responses to administrative failure rather than deliberate governance designs, which explains why their outcomes have been neither predictable nor consistently peace-promoting. Historical methods of the kind deployed by Lar, Longbaam and extended in this paper are not optional supplements to the field. They are necessary preconditions for its adequacy as an explanatory enterprise.

A fourth implication concerns the paper's relationship to the decolonial turn in peace and conflict studies. Parashar and Schulz⁴⁷, demanded renewed intellectual engagement with colonialism's enduring everyday impact and visible continuities, arguing that despite presenting itself as a critique of liberal peace, hybridity theory has reproduced Eurocentric assumptions about what constitutes legitimate governance and whose knowledge counts as theory. This is a serious challenge. Some scholars within this tradition will argue for replacing rather than correcting the hybridity framework, because its foundational assumptions are too compromised to sustain the analytical work required. This paper's response is not to contest that critique but to demonstrate that the historical argument it advances from the archive outward represents the kind of methodological decolonisation the decolonial turn calls for. A colonial genealogy of hy-

brid security governance grounded in African archival evidence and African secondary scholarship is not adding an African case study to a Western framework. It is showing, from primary sources, that the colonial origins of hybrid security in the Middle Belt require a fundamental revision of the framework's temporal and explanatory assumptions. The decolonial argument and the historical argument are, at this level, complementary rather than competing.

Conclusion

This paper has argued that hybrid conflict management in Nigeria's Middle Belt is not a post-Cold War phenomenon. Its structural preconditions were established in the 1920s and 1930s through the dual administrative architecture of British colonial governance and the institutional inadequacy of the *Yan Doka* for managing intergroup conflict. Those preconditions were institutionalised as a working hybrid architecture during the decolonisation decade of the late 1940s and 1950s, when constitutional incentives, post-war demographic change, and the strategic agency of educated elites and traditional rulers consolidated the tripartite conflict management structure that postcolonial governments inherited. Post-independence shocks, including the Civil War, the dismantling of the NAPF, and the Structural Adjustment Programme, deepened rather than created these arrangements.

⁴⁷ Swati Parashar and Michael Schulz, 'Colonial Legacies, Postcolonial "Selfhood" and the (Un)Doing of Africa', *Third*

World Quarterly 42, no. 5 (4 May 2021): 867–81, doi:10.1080/01436597.2021.1903313.

Gloria Longbaam-Alli (PhD)

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The paper has built on two genealogies of hybrid governance in the same region. It extends Jimam Lar's historical genealogy of plural policing in Plateau State, pushing it back to the structural preconditions of the 1920s and 1930s and connecting it to the international hybridity literature that Lar does not enter. It draws equally on the author's prior empirical documentation of state and non-state dynamics across Plateau, Benue, and Nasarawa from 1957 to 2018, whose oral history research independently corroborates the post-independence deepening of the colonial architecture and reveals that women developed a fourth conflict management mode through organised protest, cross-religious coalition, and intelligence work, operating outside and alongside the official tripartite structure. That the colonial architecture was constituted as an exclusively male domain, and that women consequently built their own conflict management repertoire around it, is a finding neither the policing genealogy nor the hybridity literature has registered. The tripartite structure was not merely a formal institutional inheritance. It was also a gendered one, and the women who worked around it were not peripheral actors but structurally necessary

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supplements to a system that could not function at the community level without them.

The broader implication reaches beyond the Middle Belt. Across sub-Saharan Africa, hybrid security arrangements that the peacebuilding literature treats as contemporary phenomena have colonial antecedents that remain systematically underexamined. Recovering those genealogies requires archival research, oral history, and genuine engagement between peace studies and African historical scholarship, and it requires attention to whose conflict management labour those genealogies have rendered invisible. It also requires scholars in the hybridity literature to take seriously the methodological challenge Cooper levels at Mamdani, which is to account for what happened in between, in the decisive decades when structural preconditions became working institutions. Before liberal peace, there was colonial governance; and before hybrid security became a framework for understanding contemporary Africa, it was a condition that colonialism produced, the late-colonial period institutionalised, and women navigated on terms the architecture had never designed for them.

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Gloria Longbaam-Alli (PhD)

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Gloria Longbaam-Alli (PhD)

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